

Social Innovation & Circular Construction / D6.1

WP 6, T 6.1

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
Acronym	Explanation
AACC	Alkali-activated cement-based concrete
ABE	Attribute-Based Encryption
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Model
CE	Circular Economy
CC	Circular Construction
CCC	Circular Construction Cluster
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPP	Digital Product Passport
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
NEB	New European Bauhaus
SI	Social Innovation
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document outlines the RECONSTRUCT approach to social innovation by:

- Framing key concepts (circular economy, circular construction and social innovation) through an explorative literature review;
- Outlining the project's stakeholder engagement approach and the dynamic co-creation process that has been adopted through the lens of social innovation;
- Describing the outputs of a series of collaborative road mapping workshops carried out with the project partners;
- Providing the next steps to implement a dynamic learning agenda.

The exploration of the seminal literature led to identify some challenges concerning the key concepts mentioned above. Specifically, it emerged that, in the construction industry, fundamental changes can occur by systematically engaging stakeholders in a dynamic co-creation process.

RECONSTRUCT adopts a structured stakeholder engagement approach that has been implemented in two steps:

1. Stakeholder identification and mapping in the demonstration sites (Bruxelles and Barcelona);
2. Collaborative road mapping workshops based on the internal research perspectives of consortium partners.

One of the main outputs of the stakeholder identification and mapping workshops in the demo sites, was that the local communities are not the primary object of co-creation. This is because the demos are large-scale mock-ups (from 20 to 40 square metres) and do not incorporate participation from civil society. Demos must be considered as mock-ups for prototyping and testing of RECONSTRUCT technical solutions, and will not be co-created with external stakeholders like a typical New European Bauhaus (NEB) project. This implies an important shift concerning the overall engagement strategy. A collaborative stakeholder approach has been implemented at the WP level as a support to deliver the outcomes of the different WPs. By adopting collaborative road mapping as the primary approach, RECONSTRUCT integrates social innovation through an approach that allows both direct engagement of consortium partners and indirect support for engagement activities with external stakeholders. D6.1 describes that the way to work with external stakeholders will be to set up a dynamic learning agenda with them, setting key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress on learning goals. A preliminary monitoring framework is introduced as well as an overview of the next steps within T6.1 and T6.2.

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1 Introduction

This document outlines RECONSTRUCT's stakeholder engagement strategy, emphasizing the **collaborative approach** adopted in the frame of T6.1, to set up a **learning agenda** between the consortium partners and the external stakeholders in the regional clusters.

As highlighted in the literature, several barriers and challenges should be considered in relation to the adoption of circular economy and circular construction. In this context, social innovation and co-creation are effective mechanisms to overcome barriers and facilitate stakeholder collaboration that greatly impact social innovation initiatives. However, their involvement may sometimes introduce new challenges, particularly in complex projects such as RECONSTRUCT.

Central to RECONSTRUCT's stakeholder engagement strategy is the implementation of a collaborative road mapping process that facilitates partner involvement within and across the project's various work packages (WPs), as well as with external partners. Anchored in "innovative frames" and fostering collaboration and brainstorming, this approach empowers project partners to identify goals, stakeholders involved and potential engagement strategies.

By adopting collaborative road mapping as the primary method, RECONSTRUCT **integrates social innovation through a collaborative approach** that allows both direct engagement of consortium partners and indirect support for engagement activities with external stakeholders.

In RECONSTRUCT, the engagement of consortium partners is key to:

1. Better identify the objectives for various project phases and activities concerning stakeholder engagement, such as the potential uptake of solutions by companies working in the construction sector;
2. Identify the stakeholders to engage with and the most effective levels of engagement (e.g. collaboration and consultation desired at the cluster level, particularly with regional stakeholders in Spain and Belgium);
3. Establish an innovative process of brainstorming and collaboration among project partners to develop a cohesive stakeholder engagement strategy.

Practically, this translates into the recurrent implementation of the collaborative road mapping process, as shown in Figure 1 below.

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Figure 1: RECONSTRUCT approach to stakeholders' engagement (VUB, 2023)

The starting point of this process was the identification of key stakeholders involved in the demo sites. The **stakeholder mapping** exercise was carried out in collaboration with WP7 through workshops (November 2023). Applying the "**quadruple helix**" categorisation and innovation model to include academia, industry, government, and civil society as key players in fostering collaborative innovation and sustainable development (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009), a comprehensive list of identified stakeholders in each demo region was developed.

The outcomes of the workshops emphasize that, while a wide range of stakeholders can be mapped and potentially be engaged at the government, industry and academic levels, civil society is less likely to be represented. A **stakeholder engagement roadmap** – through collaborative road mapping – was then designed to understand the research agenda at the WP level as well as which stakeholders will interact with whom at what level (demonstration, cluster and communication) and who comes from the stakeholder mapping.

As part of the cluster action plan, the external **stakeholders' expectations** will be assessed through a survey, in collaboration with WP7. This entails setting the baseline for the monitoring process as they will be asked about their place in the transition curve (e.g. whether they are already experts in digital workflows), their interests in RECONSTRUCT's main research topics (e.g. material innovation, digital workflow etc.) and preferred level of engagement. External stakeholders will also receive an overview of what to expect in the coming years, based on the cluster action plan. Both stakeholders' expectations and acceptance will feed into D6.2.

This will lead to the development of a **dynamic learning agenda** with key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress on short-term learning goals without losing sight of the overall project objectives.

It should be noted that D6.1 is focused on the first two steps, namely the processes and the outputs of the stakeholder mapping exercise and the stakeholder engagement roadmap workshops.

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1.1 Purpose of the document

This document outlines the overarching strategy for social innovation and stakeholder engagement within the RECONSTRUCT project. It primarily delves into the outcomes derived from a series of workshops conducted at both the demo and Work Package (WP) levels. While D6.1 primarily targets project partners, it also holds significance for external parties keen on exploring the advantages of the aforementioned process.

1.2 Relation to other activities

The social innovation strategy described in D6.1 is the first building block of the social innovation and replication strategy of WP6.

Specifically:

- T6.1 paves the way for the learning agenda between the consortium partners and the external stakeholders in the regional clusters;
- T6.2 monitors and updates the agenda by focusing on expectations and acceptance and identifying the mismatches between design logic and user logic;
- T.6.3 synthesises learning for replication.

The work carried out in T6.1 is also relevant to the activities of T4.3 and T4.4, which are focused on setting up the demo sites of Brussels and Barcelona. Possible engagement and co-creation activities with external stakeholders, which may be carried out in the demos, will be identified through the implementation of collaborative road mapping.

The stakeholders identified and mapped in the workshops carried out in the frame of T6.1 will feed into an actionable GDPR-compliant stakeholder database and will be used within T7.1 and T7.4.

Additionally, T7.3 “Set up Circular Construction Cluster and link to Circular Cities and Regions Initiative”, is closely linked to T6.1 as stakeholders involved in the Circular Construction Clusters (CCC) can be engaged in the collaborative road mapping activities.

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1.3 Structure of the document

D6.1 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 describes circular economy and circular construction as two emerging concepts to address the prevailing environmental and societal challenges. Additionally, it introduces social innovation and co-creation as effective mechanisms to facilitate stakeholder engagement;
- Section 3 describes the stakeholder engagement approach in RECONSTRUCT by framing it as a social innovation (SI) process and by focusing on the outputs of a series of workshops carried out with project partners. Moreover, it introduces the monitoring framework that will be adopted;
- Section 3 outlines upcoming activities and next steps;
- Annexe 1 reports on the stakeholders identified in the workshops;
- Annex 2 provides screenshots and links to the Miro boards used by partners during the workshops.

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2 Circular construction and social innovation: framing concepts

Section 2 reports the ins and outs of circular economy (CE) and circular construction (CC) as two emerging concepts to address the prevailing environmental and societal challenges (2.1). Based on the seminal literature review, this section also uncovers the challenges of adopting these strategies (2.2 and 2.3) due to the lack of awareness among the different stakeholders. Additionally, it then introduces social innovation (SI) and co-creation as effective mechanisms to fill this gap and facilitate stakeholder collaboration (2.4).

2.1 Introduction

Climate change and the depletion of virgin resources require a fundamental shift in how individuals, businesses, and governments interact with the environment, as traditional government methods frequently fall short, often resulting in practices like "green-washing" in the corporate sector (Popescu *et al.*, 2022). Companies tend to seek reputational benefits from sustainable activities rather than making substantial contributions (Gneiting and Mhlanga, 2021). Moreover, these companies also believe committing to environmental issues does not increase their profit (Ormazabal *et al.*, 2018).

This shift should consider the long-term consequences across environmental, economic, and social dimensions to achieve a sustainable outcome. Amongst many initiatives to address this urgency, the CE emerges as a valuable framework for fostering sustainability and resource efficiency.

The construction industry significantly contributes to the world's economic growth caused by urbanisation and the increasing demand for residential buildings. However, this industry globally is responsible for significant environmental degradation, accounting for significant resource consumption, energy usage, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Estokova *et al.*, 2023). The construction industry's significant consumption of natural resources and role in global solid waste generation underscores the urgent need for transformative models. In line with other CE initiatives, CC has emerged as a promising solution in response to construction challenges (Hossain *et al.*, 2020); where the traditional linear 'take, make, dispose' model prevails, the CC offers a strategic approach to resource management. Transitioning to a circular model is crucial for sustainability in construction practices and aligns with broader global goals, including the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Droege *et al.*, 2021). This regenerative circular model desires to maintain materials in a closed loop, preserving their highest value and substituting them with sustainable alternatives when necessary.

However, transitioning the entire construction sector into a full CE, like other profound shifts in human societies, is a gradual process that unfolds in multiple progressive steps. There is

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a shortage of complete evaluations related to implementing CE practices in construction projects and a lack of a comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of CE principles when applied to building projects (Hossain *et al.*, 2020). The fragmented knowledge and diverse implementation approaches hinder broad adoption across this sector (Shashi *et al.*, 2023; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

Industries, governments, and academia operate independently from each other; with different decision-making speeds, worldviews, values, and priorities. Although they frequently communicate, it requires purposeful efforts and actions to drive beyond discussion and commit to action (McDonogh, 2014). To this end, cultivating a culture of innovation that emphasises diversity, open communication, and experimentation can foster an environment conducive to the emergence of fresh and revolutionary combinations of ideas and approaches. This innovative culture not only facilitates SI but also enhances the resilience of intricate systems. Such a culture encourages positive change and adaptability, enabling these systems to thrive despite uncertainties and challenges (Frances Westley, 2013). Therefore, collaboration is crucial for achieving a CC industry, as the production and systems cycles involve interdependencies among multiple stakeholders (Scheuer, 2019). As such, CC needs new business models, technologies, partnerships, and economic development opportunities (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). In this respect, co-creation involving active and systematic engagement and collaboration of stakeholders throughout the service production process is crucial for CC.

Departing from traditional innovation theories focused on technology push or market pull, co-creation introduces the concept of 'contextual push' or 'people insights push.' This approach transcends visible demands and technical possibilities, emphasizing the understanding of tacit and latent needs, ultimately leading to more meaningful innovation (Mulder and Stappers, 2009, p.6). Therefore, the shift towards co-creation prompts a revision of governance structures, challenging conventional hierarchies and distinctions between experts and non-experts. This transformative process enhances innovation by gaining valuable insights into users' needs and contributes to more effective and sustainable product development.

2.2 Circular economy and the implementation challenges

The cradle-to-the-gate concept of the existing linear economic models works based on the production of virgin resources and disposal of landfills. The prominence of this approach since the Industrial Revolution led to decreasing virgin resources and unmanageable environmental pollution. As a paradigm shift, CE is introduced as an economic model that supports sustainability through efficient resource and waste management by sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing, and recycling resources in a closed loop.

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The concept of a CE encompasses a comprehensive approach. This model can be summarised as three fundamental principles: (1) Ensuring the protection and enhancement of natural resources requires careful management of finite reserves and a mindful approach to utilise renewable resources in a balanced manner; (2) Maximise resource efficiency by constantly cycling products, components, and materials at their highest utility in both technical and biological systems; (3) Improve the effectiveness of the foster system by identifying and eliminating any negative impacts (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013; van Stijn and Gruis, 2020). CE contributes to several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including energy, economic growth, sustainable cities, sustainable consumption and production, climate change, oceans, and life on land (Global Goals, 2016).

Among several frameworks regarding CE, the ReSOLVE framework aims to achieve circularity through six main actions: Regenerate, Share, Optimise, Loop, Virtualise, and Exchange (McKinsey, 2015).

Transitioning to a CE necessitates a collective change in behaviour, mindset, and business practices (Chhimwal *et al.*, 2022; Salvioni and Almici, 2020), as implementing CE entails addressing many challenges and barriers. Linder and Williander (2015) highlighted operational challenges, proactive assessment difficulties, risk management, and product obsolescence as the main obstacles in circular business models.

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However, CE remains an unclear concept for many people, with fragmented knowledge and varied implementation approaches (Chhimwal *et al.*, 2022; Korhonen *et al.*, 2018; Singh *et al.*, 2021). The reviewed literature reveals a gap between theoretical concepts and their practical application, which points out the importance of empirically validating these frameworks to ensure their effectiveness. There is a need for a more comprehensive framework that considers value retention and broader social, economic, and environmental impacts for a meaningful assessment of CE strategies (Chhimwal *et al.*, 2022).

Some of the main barriers and challenges are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Synthesis of barriers and challenges to CE in scholarship

Source: WP6

2.3 Circular construction and the implementation challenges

The construction sector is still beginning to adopt circularity, and a clear and unified definition is needed (Ossio *et al.*, 2023). Nevertheless, Pomponi and Moncaster (2017) defined CC as 'places designed, planned, built, operated, maintained, and deconstructed in a manner consistent with CE principles' (p. 711). Creating circular buildings involves four actions: (i) implementing a new process design that integrates various disciplines in the supply chain from the outset, (ii) collaboratively using a co-creation strategy to craft an ambitious vision, (iii) extending responsibilities to stakeholders throughout the entire building supply chain, and (iv) adopting new business and ownership models (Leising *et al.*, 2018).

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Designing buildings in a CE manner also involves employing modularity, adaptability, flexibility, and deconstruction or disassembly strategies. These design strategies enable higher performance while maintaining the value of building materials and components (Roberts *et al.*, 2023). This design method aligns with CE principles, emphasising converting building waste into valuable resources within the built environment.

Conducting a multidisciplinary approach, material selection, better design practices, reuse of embodied carbon-intensive materials, policy support, and comprehensive LCAs are the main factors for mitigating and reducing embodied carbon in the built environment (Pomponi and Moncaster, 2016). The importance of using recycled materials, regulatory intervention to achieve circularity, addressing supply chain complexities for reducing carbon emissions, and investing in training for the construction industry also are highlighted (Illankoon and Vithanage, 2023). The UK Green Building Council (UK GBC, 2023) underscored the critical imperatives for maximising reuse, optimising design, promoting standardisation, embracing product-as-a-service models, and minimising environmental impact and waste in their analysis of circular construction.

However, there has been a growing movement in the construction industry towards employing circular models recently. Nevertheless, many individuals still consider CC costly, discouraging them from investing in it (Braakman *et al.*, 2021). Besides, although the CE is considered a promising strategy for achieving sustainability in the construction industry, there is a recognised challenge in understanding how to apply this concept effectively in the construction sector (Antwi-Afari *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, many individuals perceive CC as being solely focused on waste management (Ossio *et al.*, 2023).

As a result, implementing CE principles in the construction industry involves considerable barriers and challenges. The reviewed literature reveals that there is a lack of cohesive knowledge regarding the implementation of CE principles in the construction industry. These challenges are not confined to a single section; rather, they permeate across all sectors (Charef *et al.*, 2021). These barriers are cultural, social, environmental, economic, technical, and technological (Tutu *et al.*, 2022). On top of these barriers, there is a lack of integrated policy-making frameworks to manage construction projects based on CE (Yu *et al.*, 2022). In addition, there is a lack of awareness, knowledge, and motivation between construction members when implementing CE principles in construction projects, the absence of incentives to design projects following CE principles, the non-involvement of contractors and suppliers, the use of materials that do not follow CE principles, the absence of certification for reused materials, lack of market recovery mechanisms, and prevailing procurement strategies (AlJaber *et al.*, 2024, Ahmed *et al.*, 2023; Balador *et al.*, 2020). Some other barriers are a lack of government support (Charef *et al.*, 2021), perceiving second-hand materials as substandard, lack of trust and acceptance of reclaimed materials, inadequate market value, limited design code, and a focus on using reclaimed materials, and lack of education on CE strategies among stakeholders (Tutu *et al.*, 2022; Hossain *et al.*, 2020).

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These challenges are merely a subset of the numerous obstacles to implementing CE principles in the construction industry.

According to these multidimensional barriers, shifting from a linear economy to a circular model is challenging and requires collaboration among all sections and parties. While technological innovation is important, it cannot achieve this change alone, and reorientating the existing socio-technical regime is required. Moreover, innovations are unlikely to have a significant impact unless they are supported within their operating frameworks (Westall, 2007). Accordingly, we need technological innovation alongside SI to ensure that ideas do not become orphan innovations (Bates, 2012) that are not sustainable and scalable. To achieve this, implementing a co-creation strategy incorporating stakeholder engagement through dialogue and meeting their expectations is essential for success. This approach acknowledges each stakeholder group's unique, critical role and potential impact in advancing circularity (Charef *et al.*, 2021; Salvioni and Almici, 2020).

2.4 Social Innovation

Tackling complex issues in the CE in construction requires a holistic and multifaceted approach beyond short-term fixes, and more than current policies are needed to address long-term challenges in achieving circularity. Fostering innovation is key, encompassing both technological advancements and a societal shift towards collective action (Diepenmaat *et al.*, 2020; Herrera, 2016). This means the traditional focus on technical and economic innovations alone is insufficient to address social challenges or solve local and regional problems and needs (Howaldt *et al.*, 2017). It is crucial to shift perspectives on social change, including changes in social practices, policies, and behaviours.

This shift sets the stage where SI comes into play, democratically driving positive change and offering creative solutions to contemporary issues in a dynamic and non-linear process. SI has a clear definition in the Green Paper on Innovation (European Commission, 1995), a document by the European Commission identifying factors crucial for fostering innovation in Europe; innovation is clarified as: 'a synonym for the successful production, assimilation and exploitation of novelty in the economic and social spheres. It offers new solutions to problems, thus making it possible to meet the needs of both the individual and society and create new social relationships or collaborations' (p.1). Hubert (2010) explained that 'SIs are innovations that are social in both their ends and their means. Specifically, SIs as new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. They are innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance society's capacity to act' (p. 7).

Julie Caulier-Grice *et al.* (2012) argued that 'novelty, from ideas to implementation, meets a social need, effectiveness (p. 19), and enhances society's capacity to act' (p. 20) are the

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five main elements that should be present to define a practice as socially. They also listed the common features of SI as 'cross-sectoral, open and collaborative, grassroots and bottom-up, Pro-sumption and co-production, mutualism, creates new roles and relationships, better use of assets and resources, develops assets and capabilities' (p. 21). In this definition, the SI features include collaboration, openness, grassroots origins, end-user involvement, mutualistic principles, novel roles and relationships, and efficient resource utilization.

According to the definitions, SI is a multifaceted concept encompassing various practices and principles to address social needs through novel ideas and solutions. These solutions are characterized by their effectiveness in creating new social relationships and collaborations, enhancing society's capacity to act, and offering tangible benefits to individuals and society as a whole. This aligns with the concept of open SI as an approach that opens this process and encourages the participation of various stakeholders along the course, from generating ideas to scaling solutions (Johanna Mair and Thomas Gegenhuber, 2021). SI focuses on achieving specific social goals, including community empowerment, poverty reduction, justice, social equality, and enhanced local well-being (United Nations, 2015). Sustainable development cannot be achieved without SIs (Howaldt *et al.*, 2017). However, SI is a continuous process (Frances Westley, 2013) and is a 'marathon rather than a sprint' (Johanna Mair and Thomas Gegenhuber, 2021; p. 28). Understanding the SI process will inform us about potential challenges in each stage of this process.

2.4.1 Social innovation processes

SI does not refer to any particular sector but to innovation in creating social outputs, regardless of where they originate (Julie Caulier-Grice *et al.*, 2012). Social interactions between individuals intended to achieve specific outcomes are participatory and involve multiple actors and stakeholders with a vested interest in resolving a social issue. This process empowers the beneficiaries and produces social capital, making it an outcome in and of itself (Hubert, 2010). SIs often thrive in environments that are permissive and accepting of their initiatives. Such environments provide the freedom and flexibility for these innovations to develop and grow (Howaldt *et al.*, 2017). The idea of innovation is a collaborative effort that thrives when different actors with complementary strengths work together. Small organisations and entrepreneurs can be sources of innovative ideas, while large organisations can help bring these ideas to a broader audience, ultimately leading to the successful development and adoption of innovative products, services, or solutions (Sanzo *et al.*, 2015).

According to Bates (2012), the process of SI has three stages; the first stage is *Investigation*—defining the social challenge, determining the unmet needs, and examining opportunities to achieve them; the second stage is *Innovation*—developing a workable

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solution and a powerful, effective social business model; and third is *Implementation*—to ensure the unique solution creates shared value among all stakeholders and engages techniques to ensure that ideas do not become orphan innovations which are not sustainable and scalable at the end.

In more detail, Murray et al. (2010) identified six stages for this process that take ideas from inception to impact. They argued that these stages are not always sequential, and feedback loops exist between them. They can also be considered overlapping areas with different cultures and skills. Murray et al. (2010) believed that these stages provide a useful framework for thinking about the different kinds of support that innovators and innovations need to grow.

Figure 3: Six stages of the social innovation process

Source: Murray et al., 2010

At the first stage of the SI process, all the factors necessary for innovation should be considered. The problem must be properly framed, and its root cause must be identified for a successful solution. In the proposals stage, ideas are generated and proceed to the prototyping stage through iteration and trial and error. Coalitions can be strengthened by linking users with professionals, and conflicts, such as battles with entrenched interests, can be resolved. Agreements on measures of success are reached through these processes. In the sustaining stage, the concept becomes a practice and will be ready for scaling and diffusion. Various strategies exist for growing and spreading an innovation – from organizational growth, licensing and franchising to federations and looser diffusion. Emulation and inspiration are both vital in propagating an idea or practice. Demand mobilization is crucial for the successful spread of a new model. The speed of spreading SIs depends on network structure, innovation benefits, and decision-making uncertainty. Notably, local clustering significantly enhances the spread of SIs, often resulting in substantial welfare gains through large jumps in adoption rather than incremental improvements (Young, 2011). Various factors shape the SI process; these factors are categorized differently, including political, social, economic, cultural and institutional (Bund *et al.*, 2013). However, it is crucial to understand stakeholder engagement strategies in the SI process and co-creation innovation.

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2.4.2 The role of stakeholders' engagement in social innovation

The stakeholders are key factors in SI, co-creating the process and accomplishing the organisation's goals and objectives (Loureiro *et al.*, 2020). Proactively involving stakeholders through system-building activities in innovative processes can lead to impactful solutions for societal challenges (Diepenmat 2020; Cajaiba-Santana, 2014). Engaging with the stakeholders in the projects has many valuable outcomes, such as improving trust between the actors, anticipating potential disagreements between them, making processes more transparent and accountable, enhancing the value and quality of outcomes, and broadening the reach of the results and findings (Cottrell *et al.*, 2015). In collaborative activities with stakeholders, there are four key areas to focus on:

- Understanding the relationships between stakeholders
- Communicating with them
- Collaborative learning
- Integrative stakeholder engagement (Sachs and Kujala, 2021).

Stakeholders fall into two categories: primary and secondary, in which both groups play multifaceted roles in the SI process. Primary stakeholders are directly associated with a business, and the secondary stakeholders have an indirect connection. Identifying and engaging with both primary and secondary groups is important for managing relationships and navigating business impact (Benn *et al.*, 2016; Freeman, 2010; Loureiro *et al.*, 2020). In addition, stakeholders are also classified based on these characteristics: power, legitimacy, and urgency (Leonidou *et al.*, 2020). The reviewed literature reveals that stakeholder engagement is not a one-size-fits-all concept, and it varies among sectors, settings and projects according to the objectives.

However, engagement strategies should adapt in various ways to meet stakeholders' specific needs and expectations to optimise positive outcomes. Castelló and Lopez-Berzosa (2021) have highlighted the dynamic nature of stakeholder interactions, emphasising the necessity for ongoing communication and responsiveness as vital components of effective engagement initiatives. It should be considered that in collaborative actions, undertaking sustainable development initiatives that are unimportant to stakeholders will not produce noteworthy outcomes (Nonet *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, co-creating an innovative solution process should have value for all stakeholders involved, whether psychological or economic. Stakeholders must be able to interact directly with each other and providing platforms for their interaction is very important (Ramaswamy and Gouillart, 2010).

Two types of openness in learning through stakeholders' engagement are highlighted: participative and reflective. Participative openness encourages free expression of opinions and broad participation in decision-making but may limit learning by not challenging existing assumptions. Reflective openness involves critically examining one's thinking and questioning assumptions. However, the combination of participative and reflective openness

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can be particularly powerful, as it encourages both active participation and deeper self-reflection, leading to more meaningful learning experiences (Flood, 1998). A significant portion of exchanged knowledge in collaborative actions is tacit, shaped by shared interactions and experiences in co-creation (Mirvis *et al.*, 2016).

Kazadi *et al.* (2016) explained that a lead firm may face challenges when co-creating with multiple stakeholders simultaneously. The main challenges exist in '*finding and engaging the appropriate stakeholders for co-creation*', '*conflict stemming from stakeholder diversity*' (conflict even between the people from the same firm), and '*management of stakeholder co-created knowledge*' (p. 533). Divergent goals and interests among the stakeholders, motivating different stakeholder types to work together, difficulties in communication, and distrust, doubts, and uncertainties between the stakeholders are other challenges in the co-creation process with multiple stakeholders involved (Kazadi *et al.* 2016; Waligo *et al.*, 2014). Waligo *et al.* (2014) also hinted at the conflict over value appropriation in co-creation.

Therefore, effective stakeholder management is crucial and deserves attention. When managing co-creation with a diverse group, it is crucial to understand the potential conflicts and complexities that may arise. To successfully manage such a group, tailored management capabilities that account for the varied goals, communication styles, trust dynamics, and potential conflicts among diverse participants are necessary. However, harmonizing conflicting views before a project starts is a proactive and strategic approach to preventing potential challenges and ensuring a smooth project initiation (Kazadi *et al.*, 2016).

2.4.3 Barriers to Social Innovation Implementation

The development of SI is an intricate process influenced by the dynamic between systems and the individuals operating within them (Antadze and Westley, 2010). Successful SI should be systematic, sustainable, self-organized, scalable and replicable (Nick Jankel, 2010). Factors influencing SI include internal, external (Antadze and Westley, 2010), structural and agency factors (Mendes *et al.*, 2012). Internal attributes impacting SI are as follows: openness to novelty, consciousness, responsibility, proactive thinking, lifelong learning, positive experience, passivity, and conservative thinking (Oganisjana *et al.*, 2015). External factors, however, include power distance and bureaucracy (Oganisjana *et al.*, 2015). Structural barriers are associated with the complexity and uncertainty of social processes and their consequences on other contextual characteristics—such as social, political, economic, and technological factors—in which social innovators operate. Barriers to agency in SI processes arise from the actions and characteristics of individuals and organizations involved and their interactions (Mendes *et al.*, 2012). Mendes *et al.* (2012) argued that structural factors influence agency, but agencies through individuals and organizations can leverage their agency to change these factors by reinforcing their role in impeding SI or by overcoming this role and developing SIs.

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However, social innovators face barriers commonly connected to an incompatible regulatory culture (Hubert, 2010). Hubert (2010) outlines the barriers to the SI process, classifying them into four groups:

- Organizational culture and system design, including risk-averse and cautious organizational cultures and closed systems;
- Lack of collaboration and networking, characterized by single-issue solutions and clusters of organizations lacking mutual awareness, communication, networking, and trust;
- Fragmented capacities, such as resources, infrastructures, and intermediaries, alongside issues with skills (training, design tools, monitoring, validation, and evaluation);
- Funding and financial support are characterized by insufficient stable, seamless, and sustainable funding.

Among these mentioned barriers, Hubert underscored the most commonly raised issues as funding, governance, skills, and the measurement of SI.

Carvache-Franco et al. (2018) identified important enablers for SI, as Rodríguez Herrera and Alvarado (2008) outlined. These include (a) associativity, highlighting the capacity for the organization of collective efforts, with a focus on engaging participants; (b) Integrality, involving the combination and application of various forms of knowledge, experiences, and solutions; (c) Sustainability, the ability to maintain initiatives over time through innovative solutions that effectively manage limited resources, which is crucial for allowing further adoption; (d) Innovation, which refers to impactful collective actions that address specific issues via the introduction of novel processes, techniques, or organizational methods; and (e) Replicability, the capability to transfer insights and outcomes from one innovative endeavour to others in varying contexts, enabling broader application and impact.

Therefore, the absence of effective social learning poses a hurdle for SI, necessitating collaboration among diverse social groups to establish socially desirable goals (McLoughlin and Preece, 2010). As mentioned, the type of innovation also has a significant impact on successful SI. Many promising ideas fail to evolve into SI due to high costs, a lack of demand, or inadequate performance compared to existing options (Mendes *et al.*, 2012). Rogers (1983) refined our understanding by specifying characteristics innovations must maintain to be adopted by target communities. Rogers's (1983) framework underscores the need for innovations to offer clear and relative advantages aligned with societal values, exhibit a high degree of compatibility with existing values, maintain manageable complexity, and provide trialability, which offers more certainty to individuals considering their adoption. In addition, the framework emphasizes that observability—the ease with which the results of an innovation can be measured and analyzed by others—is also essential (p. 15). Loureiro et al. (2020) identified three key mechanisms that can facilitate stakeholder interactions in the innovation process: quality of information exchange, affinity, and power.

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Importantly, in collaboration activities, a significant challenge also arises from the lack of a common mutual understanding. To address this obstacle, stakeholders must adopt a common language and standard terminology, fostering more effective and unified solutions (Gil-Marín *et al.*, 2022). However, better communication and coordination are crucial among individuals and organizations, enhancing the SI landscape. Nevertheless, caution is warranted, as attempting to scale up too quickly can prove ineffective and inappropriate (Howaldt *et al.*, 2017). Key points in this regard include the importance of networking and centralized coordination, which can streamline efforts, reduce duplication, and ensure the efficient use of resources (Živojinović *et al.*, 2023).

Therefore, SI is influenced by a dynamic collection of factors, where internal characteristics like openness to innovation and external forces such as regulatory restrictions play crucial roles. The development of SI faces barriers, including conservative organizational cultures, lack of collaboration, fragmented resources, knowledge and skills, and inadequate funding. At the same time, it benefits from enablers like collective effort organization, diverse knowledge application, and the ability to sustain and replicate initiatives. To be successful, overcoming these challenges requires effective social learning, strategic stakeholder selection and collaboration emphasizing clear communication and mutual understanding, and a careful approach to scaling up. The characteristics that make innovations successful—such as compatibility with existing values, simplicity, and observability—alongside mechanisms like quality information exchange foster an ecosystem helping to adopt and expand SI.

In conclusion, traditional construction strategies have primarily focused on cost, time, and quality, often neglecting the environmental impacts of the practices. The industry follows linear business models characterized by the extraction of virgin resources without consideration for long-term consequences, transforming these resources into high-energy construction materials and ultimately discarding them into landfills. Recently, the construction industry has been recognized for its pivotal role in the shift toward CC, aiming to reduce resource consumption, extend the lifespan of materials, and maintain their value at the highest level. Efforts to minimize waste and promote material reusability have been initiated, yet a systematic perspective remains necessary (Shojaei *et al.*, 2021) due to the diversity of implementation approaches (Shashi *et al.*, 2023; Singh *et al.*, 2021; Hossain *et al.*, 2020) and isolated efforts (Shojaei *et al.*, 2021). As Goulding and Rahimian (2019) advocated, a transformative change requires multiple factors, including stakeholder awareness, supply chain readiness, cultural perception shifts, viable business models/solutions, and industry upskilling across design, manufacturing, and construction phases. Additionally, reviewing policies and market innovations is crucial to understanding the contextual culture, addressing environmental issues transparently, and considering the impact of policies and technological advancements in decision-making processes (Tinarwo *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, to achieve sustainable goals, there should be more robust and transparent systematic mechanisms. In the construction industry, fundamental changes will occur by looking through the lens of SI and systematically engaging stakeholders in a

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dynamic co-creation process. SI serves as a key connector, transforming isolated efforts in the construction industry towards a CE into a cohesive movement for sustainable development. At its core, openness, collaboration, transparency, inclusiveness, systematic risk reduction through extensive knowledge sharing, and meaningful actions are essential aspects of the SI process. Scaling up SI requires a delicate balance between speed and effectiveness, with factors such as appropriate processing, networking, leadership, and organisational characteristics playing effective roles. It is critical to emphasize that, to achieve sustainable goals in the construction industry, there should be more robust and transparent collaborative systematic mechanisms to unite isolated efforts and diverse approaches.

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3 RECONSTRUCT

stakeholder engagement strategy

Stakeholders are indispensable players in strategic thinking. Therefore, effective stakeholder management is a critical strategic consideration beyond involving them in the project. This can directly influence the success of SI initiatives. In complex projects like RECONSTRUCT, involving various stakeholders with different characteristics, personalities, motivations, interests, and expectations can be challenging to align everyone's goals (Kazadi *et al.*, 2016). Misalignments can create significant project barriers, preventing stakeholders from working towards a shared goal. Roadmaps are utilized to conduct the 'align' and 'plan' operations to facilitate alignment (Kerr and Phaal, 2015). Roadmaps allow different stakeholder groups of RECONSTRUCT to see the bigger picture and understand how their contributions fit into the broad vision of the project (Kerr *et al.*, 2017). This ultimately results in a more cohesive and successful project outcome.

Therefore, understanding each stakeholder's needs, motivations, and potential impacts on the project's success is required. Managing and aligning different parties' expectations to project goals is also crucial. As such, RECONSTRUCT implemented a dynamic stakeholder analysis model integrating continuous engagement and adaptive stakeholders' communication strategies. To guarantee the model's success, the RECONSTRUCT comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy advocates openness, collaboration, transparency, inclusiveness, consensus, and responsiveness. A proactive approach is also crucial for such a model to address any possible conflicts in advance and utilize varied stakeholder inputs. This approach will enable RECONSTRUCT to mitigate the risks caused by stakeholder misalignment and improve the project's resilience. At its core, the lessons learned from the seminal literature reveal that the success of RECONSTRUCT hinges on an adaptive and strategic approach to stakeholder management. This approach anticipates challenges and transforms them into opportunities for deeper engagement and collaboration, thereby driving project progress and maximizing impact.

As mentioned in the Introduction the starting point of the stakeholder engagement strategy was the identification and mapping of key stakeholders involved in demo sites which was followed by the stakeholder engagement roadmap applied through collaborative road mapping with the project partners.

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Figure 4: RECONSTRUCT approach to stakeholders' engagement (VUB, 2023)

3.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping

This Section revolves around the processes and outcomes of a series of activities carried out with the partners from November 2023 to January 2024 which revolved respectively around the stakeholder identification and mapping (Sub-section 3.1), the impact on the overall RECONSTRUCT engagement strategy (Sub-sections: 3.2 and 3.3) and the outputs of the collaborative road mapping done at WP level.

Assuming a New European Bauhaus context¹, the **demonstration projects** were the starting point to map relevant stakeholders in RECONSTRUCT.

During the RECONSTRUCT project, two demos with different typologies will be built in two distinct locations: the **urban context** of the Santa Perpètua de Mogoda Castle in Barcelona and the **research context** of the Green Energy Park in Brussels. The two regions, north and south, also provide a very different setting: they have different **climatic conditions**, **building traditions** and **value chains**, and they are at different places on the **transition curve** to zero carbon. Local building codes, norms and standards further differentiate the design of the two pilots (see D4.1).

The Belgian demonstrator will be constructed on the premises of **Green Energy Park**, an innovation campus located in Zellik (Brussels), established in collaboration between Vrije Universiteit Brussel and the Brussels University Hospital.

Green Energy Park is a new hub for **multidisciplinary collaboration** providing strategic facilities for research, development and demonstration of advanced technologies. The **Living Lab Centre** of Green Energy Park provides large-scale, real-life environments where

¹ NEB, or New European Bauhaus, is an initiative launched by the European Commission in 2021 with the objective of leveraging the design capabilities in EU to support the European Green Deal policies in everyday lives of citizens in urban contexts. As such, NEB is focused on the inclusion of non-experts and local communities through design collaborative methods. More information can be found at https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

companies, knowledge institutions, governments and end users can advance new sustainable solutions in four key areas: energy & mobility, hospital of the future, smart regions and biotechnology. The Living Labs are complemented by a **training, knowledge, and experience centre** to bring innovations to the market faster.

A diverse array of stakeholders is involved in the Brussels demo. **Green Energy Park (GEP)** is the client, landowner and end-user of the building. With the help of the Department of Infrastructure at the VUB, they will manage the permit application process and coordinate the construction activities. **Holland Composites (HOL)** is the industrial partner in charge of the production and assembly of the modular, prefabricated building structure. They will also output the BIM model to test the RECONSTRUCT digital workflow. **Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)** will develop, test and deliver the new, low-carbon TRC and AAC-based floor components, that will be demonstrated in the pilot. And finally, **Societat Orgànica (SOO)** will conduct the circularity (and adaptability) analyses to assess the impact of the developed solutions, relative to current building practices.

In Brussels, the demo partners can build on existing regional stakeholder networks like the **'Living Lab circulair beton'**, and the Flemish **'betonakkoord'**, to engage external stakeholders in the RECONSTRUCT project.

The **Spanish demonstration site** will be situated in an exterior area within the grounds of Mogoda's Castle in Santa Perpetua de Mogoda, a segment of the Barcelona Metropolitan Area. This historic site is owned by Incasol, project partner and body of the Generalitat de Catalunya, operating under the Department of Territory and Sustainability. Incasol plays a pivotal role in the promotion of public residential land across Catalonia.

The demo site will become a new hub within an extended network of Spanish initiatives on innovation in construction, such as Waste Management Cluster, Cluster Edificació, Catalunya Circular: el Observatorio de Economía Circular, Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA) (Seville), CCIC - Industrialized Construction Cluster of Catalonia, the Concrete Center, Entrepreneurs Construction federation, *Asociación de centros y servicios de reutilización* (AUS).

The stakeholders involved in the Barcelona demo site span across various sectors, each playing a crucial role in its execution. Collaborating closely with INCASOL are architects who are integral to the design and implementation phases of the project. Additionally, the research sector is represented by Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL, Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción (ITEC, Catalunya), and Simbiosi Industrial S.L., contributing expertise in innovative construction techniques. From the industrial sector, COMSA Corporación and Sorigué lend their support, bringing practical experience and resources to the table.

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COMSA is interested in developing in-situ AACC concrete with a high recycled content, and dismountable AACC cement façade panels with recycled content and textile reinforcement for buildings. Sorigüe is interested in a dismountable exterior pavement with recycled content and AACC concrete for exterior applications. Such disposable solutions developed in RECONSTRUCT will be of interest to further local companies.

As mentioned above, to take a deep dive into the stakeholders involved at the demos level, RECONSTRUCT applied the "quadruple helix" innovation model to include academia, industry, government, and civil society as key players. Two stakeholder mapping workshops were carried out in November which led to interesting outcomes. The latter, as explained in the following pages, had a significant impact on RECONSTRUCT's approach to stakeholder engagement.

To identify and map stakeholders involved at the demo level in a systematic and structured manner, a series of meetings and two online workshops were organized in November 2023 (November 15 and 16), respectively with the partners involved in the Barcelona (Societat Orgànica, Sorigué, COMSA, ITEC, and CTCON, plus one representative from the Government of Catalunya, November 15) and in the Brussels demos (VUB, Green Energy Park and Holland composites, November 16).

Initial meetings were also held with the demo leaders (VUB and Societat Orgànica) to get a first overview of the key stakeholders. These were identified using the **quadruple helix** innovation model to include academia, industry, government, and civil society as key players in fostering collaborative innovation and sustainable development. Stakeholders, as shown below, were linked to various **levels of engagement**: "inform", namely those who, most likely, will be only informed about the progress of the project and/or specific solutions, "consult", namely those who will e.g. provide feedback on decisions and solutions and "collaborate" which entails a stronger level of involvement (e.g. stakeholders cooperating with project's partners). Moreover, key stakeholders were identified both in relation to the demos and to the clusters. As shown in Figure 5, "inform" has been translated into "communication".

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Figure 5: Stakeholder mapping using the quadruple helix approach (ICONS, VUB and SOO, 2023)

This first stakeholder identification and mapping exercise shed light on the need to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the demonstration sites. For this reason, as mentioned above, two online workshops were held on M6 (November 2023). The format was the same (Miro boards) but the level of detail was different. Participants were asked to make a stakeholder segmentation based on:

- the **type** of industry, institution or organisation (e.g. Engineering offices, Contractors, Clusters, Manufacturers, EU initiatives, Research Centres, Associations, etc.) and their scope (e.g. Certifications, Investors);
- the **geographical scope** (local, regional, national or European);
- the **level of expected engagement** with each stakeholder (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower)

Additionally, the exercise aimed to capture the objectives of engagement:

1. Products/solutions development;
2. The RECONSTRUCT framework for circular construction;
3. Business models;
4. Policy documents.

The workshop for the Brussels demo was held with RECONSTRUCT partner VUB and the two consortium partners involved in the demo site, the Green Energy Park and Holland Composites. The outputs of the workshop are shown in Fig 7.

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Figure 7: Outputs of the workshop with the Brussels demo partners (ICONS, VUB, 2023)

[Link](#) to the digital whiteboard on miro.com

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As depicted in the figure, civil society, labelled as ‘Citizens’ in the template, is not represented at all among the stakeholders.

Industry holds the highest representation among stakeholders, counting 81 actors over 107. The workshop allowed us to confirm how the Brussels demo can leverage an already established cluster, the *Living Lab Circulaire Beton*², which has been promoting the adoption of circular economy practices in the local industry. The Living Lab will be collaborating as the main channel of communication with the local construction industry ecosystem. The geographical scope is mainly national. The objectives of engagement proved more challenging to gauge. What can be inferred is that manufacturers will primarily engage in exploring new material innovations and business models, as they offer tools (e.g. MEMC radars) and materials (e.g. fly ash) that will be used in RECONSTRUCT. Engineering offices and contractors will serve as consultative sources for expert insights and understanding of the value chain dynamics. Finally, public authorities will be informed of project developments.

33 stakeholders were identified as priority for engagement, also specifying the level and the objectives of engagement. These stakeholders are reported in the table provided in **Annex 1**. The participants also pinpointed 19 stakeholders with whom they already have established strong connections (marked with black dots on the template): these stakeholders can serve as the initial focus for engagement within specific sectors or networks.

Figure 8: Industry partners – Bruxelles demonstration site (ICONS, VUB, 2023)

The second workshop, carried out with partners involved in the Barcelona demonstration site, led also to interesting results.

² <https://vlaanderen-circulair.be/en/cases/detail/living-lab-circular-concrete>

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As shown in Figure 9, the stakeholders are more diversified than in Brussels, with no overwhelming majority. Concerning the geographical scope, 37 stakeholders are active on the regional level and 20 on the national level.

In Barcelona, industrial stakeholders encompass building, manufacturing, and construction demolition waste (CDW) management companies, but also associations, federations and clusters. These latter groups will be engaged with the aim of disseminating and spreading RECONSTRUCT new solutions within the local industrial landscape.

Unlike Brussels, the public authorities are mostly regional and local, thus mostly pertaining to Catalunya. The engagement objectives with regional authorities are twofold: firstly, will be engaged in devising tools and indicators for circularity frameworks, while most will be involved in disseminating RECONSTRUCT results. A handful of national-level public stakeholders play a crucial role in identifying regulatory barriers to circular supply chains and developing a framework for public construction projects.

Knowledge-producing stakeholders, labelled as 'Academic,' include universities, technical institutions, research centres, and EU initiatives. Additionally, civil society organizations, labelled as 'Citizens,' were identified, with many of them still linked to industrial activities, such as professional associations and bodies. Hence, they cannot be considered as "citizens" as such.

Regarding engagement objectives, while data collection on 'Academic' and civil society stakeholders was not feasible, none of them were prioritized for engagement activities. Participants selected 11 stakeholders for prioritized engagement, as listed in the table provided in Annex 1.

Furthermore, the workshop shed light on the potential of leveraging Catalunya Circular, a digital platform on circular economy established by the Government of Catalunya in 2018³. This platform serves as a matchmaker and knowledge hub for all local initiatives focused on circular economy endeavours.

Overall, the stakeholder identification and mapping allowed to map 189 stakeholders, respectively 107 for Brussels and 71 for Barcelona, and 5 stakeholders in common between the two demo sites, which are:

- ACE (European Architect Council);
- Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC);
- Arup (consultancy on design and engineering);
- European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform;
- Fellows and pilots from CCRI;
- New European Bauhaus (NEB).

³ https://mediambient.gencat.cat/ca/05_ambits_dactuacio/empresa_i_produccio_sostenible/economia_verda/catalunya_circular/

Figure 9: Outputs of the workshop with the Barcelona demo partners (ICONS, SOO, 2023)

	Government				Industry				Academic				Citizen											
	Municipal	Regional	National	European	Associations	Building companies	Clusters	Manufacturers	Federations	Software developers	Investors	Urban Movers - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants, other initiatives	Certifications	EU initiatives	Research Centres	SME	Technical institutions	Universities	Associations	Blue Collar Workers	Communication SMEs	Federations	Professional bodies	Other
<p>Government</p> <p>As the main stakeholders, we work in order to coordinate and align the different initiatives.</p> <p>Level of engagement: SYSTEM</p> <p>Objectives of engagement:</p>	[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]											
<p>Industry</p> <p>As the main stakeholders, we work in order to coordinate and align the different initiatives.</p> <p>Geographical scope:</p> <p>Level of engagement:</p> <p>Objectives of engagement:</p>	[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]											
<p>Academic</p> <p>As the main stakeholders, we work in order to coordinate and align the different initiatives.</p> <p>Geographical scope:</p> <p>Level of engagement:</p> <p>Objectives of engagement:</p>	[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]											
<p>Citizen</p> <p>As the main stakeholders, we work in order to coordinate and align the different initiatives.</p> <p>Geographical scope:</p> <p>Level of engagement:</p> <p>Objectives of engagement:</p>	[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]				[Stakeholders, Objectives, Geographical scope, Level of engagement, Objectives of engagement]											

[Link](#) to the digital whiteboard on miro.com

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3.2 Impact on RECONSTRUCT stakeholder engagement strategy

The outcomes of the workshops emphasize that, while a wide range of stakeholders can be mapped and potentially be engaged at the government, industry and academic levels, civil society is less likely to be represented.

Brussels has an established stakeholder cluster on the topic of circular concrete, with the [living lab circulair beton](#) and the [betonakkoord](#), a manifesto piloted by the government and signed by many of the key stakeholders. In Barcelona, the stakeholders are not that far yet in the transition curve, but platforms like [Catalunya Circular](#) could play a similar role, with the regional government gathering stakeholders around this topic as they have done with the '[pacte per a la moda circular](#)'.

Local communities will not be the primary partners for co-creation, as the outputs show. This is because the demos are not like a typical urban scale NEB-project, where, sustainable solutions are developed between local governments, research institutions and civil associations. Because of their modest scale, the RECONSTRUCT demos should rather be considered as large-scale mock-ups (about 50 m²). That is why they will not incorporate in the development phase, participation from civil society.

The demos have to be considered as mock-ups to prototype and test the RECONSTRUCT technical solutions, and will not be co-created with external stakeholders like a typical NEB project. As such, demos are no longer the main objective of social innovation, but **a means of research and dissemination**.

This implies an important shift concerning the overall engagement strategy:

1. A collaborative stakeholder approach is implemented at the WP level as a support to deliver the outcomes of the different WPs. This repositions the demos as a method rather than a primary objective, since, as mentioned above, the demos should be considered as means of research and dissemination rather than the main objectives of social innovation. An illustration of the conflicts arising from this shift in approach is evident in our key performance indicator (KPI) of engaging 100 participants, who will primarily be sector stakeholders aligned with the clusters, rather than civil stakeholders involved in the demos;
2. By adopting collaborative roadmapping as the primary approach, RECONSTRUCT integrates social innovation through an approach that allows both direct engagement of consortium partners and indirect support for engagement activities with external stakeholders.

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The objectives to be collaboratively developed with external stakeholders will constitute the various deliverables within the work packages (WPs).

3. The way to work with external stakeholders will be to set up a **dynamic learning agenda** with them, setting key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress on short-term learning goals without losing sight of the overall project objectives. This entails that participants are asked to rephrase potential issues in terms of a question to be answered, and progress on answering these questions is reflected upon at subsequent meetings. Learning questions on the agenda may change in order of importance, be removed or added to as the project develops and new challenges are identified, ensuring that learning goals remain relevant to the project's objective, and each of the stakeholders involved.

The stakeholders identified and mapped in the workshops will feed into an actionable **GDPR-compliant stakeholder database** and will be used within T7.1 and T7.4. It will include segmentations per stakeholder type, the geographical working area, relevant key exploitation results (KERs) for each stakeholder type, preferred dissemination channels and formats, and the partner responsible for each contact.

This database aims to empower project partners to carry out the dissemination of project results towards the identified entities and their direct contacts. Besides, this will avoid overlaps in the communication among partners towards those stakeholders.

In addition, this database will be used for the same purpose by the **Local D&C desks** – represented by GEP for the Brussels demo case, and by INCASOL for the one located in Barcelona, under the coordination of SOO. They are focused to identify and contact local stakeholders whose level of engagement is marked as “inform”.

The internal research perspectives of the project partners (namely, the collaborative stakeholder approach mentioned above) have been explored through four collaborative road mapping workshops conducted respectively with WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP5, which aimed to:

- Confirm the WP objectives and the task deliverables that WP partners aim to achieve;
- Draw the sequence of actions, identifying interactions with external stakeholders on three levels, resumed in Figure 11:
 - at the **demo level**, including demo materials and components data related to the digital passport in a database, collaborating with other demo partners (WP1, WP3 and WP5). This level is the one that leverages the most co-design and collaborative activities with stakeholders;
 - Collaboration and consultation are desired at the **cluster level**, particularly with regional stakeholders in Spain and Belgium. For instance, conducting surveys with external experts to gather insights on the structure of the digital

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- passport. This data can be cross-referenced with the outcomes of the workshops detailed in section 3.4;
- o Identifying the **broadest audience** to be informed about the primary output, like the Circular Cities & Regions Initiative (CCRI). This level includes also **scientific engagement**, as it pertains to the engagement with stakeholders who might interested in the knowledge and methodologies developed by the project. It is also characterised by a relatively low level of engagement, with mostly, one-way passage of knowledge and information from the project to stakeholders.

Figure 10: Collaborative road mapping approach (VUB, 2023)

The outputs of the workshops are outlined in Section 3.4

3.3 Outputs of the collaborative road mapping workshops

Participants were tasked with completing a timeline template outlining activities planned within their respective WPs. A customized template (Fig. 12) was designed to collect relevant information while aligning with participants' existing mental models and building upon them, fostering continuity and coherence with previous activities (Phaal et al., 2004).

Figure 11: Example of template used in the workshops (ICONS, VUB, 2024)

Initially, participants were tasked with confirming the objectives of the work packages (WPs). Subsequently, for each task within the WPs, participants were repeatedly asked to validate the task objectives. The third step involved participants describing the activities planned to achieve these objectives (noted on black sticky notes as "WHAT" on the template) and identifying both internal and external stakeholders to engage for each activity (noted on black sticky notes as "WHO").

The fourth and final step entailed placing each activity on the project timeline while determining the level of engagement required. This final step, in particular, prompted discussions with WP partners, serving as a preliminary brainstorming session on potential new approaches to engaging external stakeholders. Further details are provided in the subsections below.

3.3.1 WP1 - AI-based sourcing and characterization of materials and waste

WP1 will engage external stakeholders to align the AI solutions they are developing with the needs and requirements of the construction value chain. The primary objective is to integrate the AI system into the processes that facilitate the reuse of CDW across various construction sites and industrial actors.

The breakdown of activities planned by partners in WP1 is presented in Table 1 below. Activities are categorised per task in the corresponding rows and per demo, cluster and scientific level in the columns. The activities that entail a form of engagement consistent with social innovation approaches are underlined, with five activities identified as potential avenues of social innovation within the circular construction sector.

T1.1 - Data collection, design and validation of the AI-based sourcing modules

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In this task, the activity in which stakeholder engagement can be developed further is *Reach out to other construction contractors through a questionnaire* at M22-M26 at the Cluster level. The task leader, BUL, has considered checking the interest of construction contractors in the AI-based sourcing modules to evaluate their possible market uptake through a questionnaire; it may be possible to integrate such consultation with more collaborative methods, as already done in open innovation practices, which would allow a higher level of engagement from external stakeholders and a higher reliability of data collected (Perkmann et al., 2007).

T1.5 - Optimization of CDW and other waste valorisation routes

The most relevant activities for engagement in WP1 are *Analysis of valorisation routes for materials* at M13 and *Benchmark of products from CDW (Construction & Demolition Waste)* at M13-M14, since both will need to engage with external stakeholders to collect data on the value chain of materials and the characteristics of CDW products. The task leader indicated that interviews or meetings were considered as methods, but there is potential to employ more collaborative approaches to facilitate interactions with external stakeholders. For instance, organizing workshops to collaboratively design material value chains with relevant stakeholders.

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Table 1: Outputs of the workshop (WP1)

	Project level	Demo level	Cluster level	Scientific engagement
Task 1.1 Leader: BUL	Literature review - BUL, UNIVPM [M1-M2]	Preliminary visit and data collection on-site - BUL, UNIVPM COMSA, SOR [M5]	<u>Reach out to other construction contractors through a questionnaire</u> – BUL [M22-M26]	Scientific publication - digitalisation and quantification of CDW – BUL [M18-M24]
	Defining the innovation goals, in contrast to existing solutions - BUL, UNIVPM [M2]	Second data collection on-site - BUL, UNIVPM COMSA, SOR [M10]		
	Assessment of data collected - BUL, UNIVPM [M5-M6]			
	Data processing, annotations - BUL, UNIVPM [M8]			
	Data processing, annotations, outputs - BUL, UNIVPM [M16]			
	Upload of output to Symbiosis platform - BUL, UNIVPM, SYM [M20]			
Task 1.2 Leader: BUL	Literature review - BUL [M1-M2]	Implementation and data collection - BUL, COMSA, SOL [M11]	Establishing contacts with data providers - COPERNICUS, UP42, SKYWATCH [M2]	Scientific publication - image processing tools for quantification of CDW – BUL [M12-M18]
	Feasibility check on-site - BUL, COMSA, SOR [M4]		Evaluating pricing and alternative solutions and providers - BUL, DETECTIA [M7-M9]	
	Proposal of selected solutions with ITEC - BUL, ITEC [M10]			

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	Data processing, annotation - BUL [M14]			
	Output uploaded to Symbiosis platform - BUL, SYM [M17]			
Task 1.3 Leader: BUL	Literature review - BUL [M2]	Survey evaluating different conditions on-site - BUL, UNIVPM, COMSA, SOR [M5]		Scientific publication - image processing tools for quantification of CDW - BUL [M12-M18]
	Phase 1 of sensors selection - BUL, UNIVPM [M4]	Data collection from demo sites, annotation, data processing – BUL [M6]		
	Phase 2 of sensors selection - BUL, UNIVPM [M9]	Visit on-site to install sensors - BUL, UNIVPM, COMSA, SOR [M10]		
	Training and implementation of model - BUL [M15]	Data collection from demo sites, annotation, data processing - BUL, UNIVPM, COMSA, SOR [M12]		
	Output uploaded to Symbiosis platform - BUL, SYM [M17]			
Task 1.4 Leader: UNIVPM	Literature review - UNIVPM, IRIS [M7]	Review of materials list for characterisation - UNIVPM, IRIS, COMSA, SOR [M8]		Scientific dissemination - preliminary monitoring system including HW and SW parts – UNIVPM [M13-M18]
	List of tests for characterisation of materials - UNIVPM, IRIS [M8]	Delivery of material samples for tests - COMSA, SOR [M10]		Scientific dissemination on preliminary results: AI models, datasets of CDW, development of measurement procedures of characterisation - UNIVPM [M13-M18]
	Design of test protocols - UNIVPM, IRIS [M8-M9]			Scientific publications - final monitoring system including HW and SW parts - UNIVPM [M24]

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	Tests execution – UNIVPM, IRIS [M10-M12]			
	Data processing - UNIVPM, IRIS [M13]			
	Design of library of materials - UNIVPM, IRIS [M13]			
	AI models for categorisation of materials - UNIVPM, BUL (even though not formally in the task) [M14]			
	Analysis of uncertainty - UNIVPM [M14]			
Task 1.5 Leader: SYM	Coding of data from previous tasks in the platform – SYM [M17-M20]	<i>Across both Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Design of list for characterisation materials</u> - BUL, UNIVPM, SOR, SYM, ITEC, COMSA, SOO [M8]</i>		
	Coding of data from T1.5 in the platform – SYM [M17-M20]	<i>Across both Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Establish a further list of external waste to be included in the materials list</u> - SYM, VUB, CTC, ITEC, COMSA, SOR [M9]</i>		
	Development of UIS decision tool (in collaboration with WP3) - ICCS, SYM [M20-M23]	<i>Across both Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Analysis of valorisation routes for materials</u> - SOR, SYM, ITEC, COMSA, SOO [M13]</i>		
			<i><u>Benchmark of products from CDW (Construction & Demolition Waste)</u> - SYM, ITEC [M13-M14]</i>	

3.3.2 WP2 - Circular construction materials & components

The engagement activities within WP2 were noted by partners as not yet fully defined, indicating a need for active support from task T6.1. These engagement efforts will focus on disseminating information about the project to potential adopters of new construction materials, potentially gathering feedback from them, and ultimately sharing data and results with the scientific community.

The output of the collaborative road mapping with WP2 partners is captured in Table 2 below. Two activities are identified as potential avenues of social innovation.

Task 2.2 - Development of precast and in-situ AACC elements

One partner (UNIVPM) suggested that it would be useful to engage external stakeholders in between M31 and M48, to collect feedback from companies potentially interested in the alkali-activated cement-based concrete (AACC), and open potential spaces for collaboration with industrial partners. The aim was framed by WP partners as informing potentially interesting stakeholders about the results of the WP2 development: nevertheless, also the possibility of organising workshops was mentioned, during which feedback from stakeholders can be collected. This will be further explored to design engagement activities aimed at fostering two-way knowledge exchange with industrial stakeholders.

Task 2.5 - Recyclability studies for the materials and components

Additional engagement activities can be proposed in Task 2.5, between M37 and M48. The motivation is again to engage external stakeholders that may be interested in the output of WP2, especially considering the construction industry. During the workshop, the task leader suggested that the activity should be anticipated by a mapping of such stakeholders across but also beyond the RECONSTRUCT clusters, which can then be invited to workshops or other activities. As in Task 2.2, the engagement can be designed to facilitate knowledge exchange with stakeholders from the construction industry.

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Table 2: Outputs of the workshop (WP2)

	Project level	Demo level	Cluster level	Scientific engagement
Task 2.1 Leader: VUB	Characterization of raw materials - VUB (FYSC) [M5-M6]	Characterise waste materials - UNIVPM, CTCON, SOR [M5-M8]		Scientific publications - VUB-UNIVPM-CTCON [M14-M33]
	Characterise and testing of alkali-activated paste - VUB (FYSC) [M5-M10]	Characterise recycled aggregates - UNIVPM, CTCON, SOR [M9-M11]		
	Develop core sandwich panel and test - VUB (FYSC) [M8-M23]	Develop mortars - UNIVPM, CTCON, SOR [M9-M23]		
	Develop and test mortar and concrete - VUB (FYSC) [M9-M23]	Develop and test concrete - UNIVPM, CTCON, SOR [M13-M23]		
Task 2.2 Leader: CTCON	Collaboration with work package 4 to define the characteristics and dimensions of the precast elements and on-situ concrete for the Barcelona demonstrator. [M1-M10]	Development of precast and in-situ AAC elements - UNIVPM, CTCON, SOR [M11]		Scientific publications – UNIVPM, CTCON [M16-M33]
	Test with composite biobased rebars [M10-M19]	<i>Across both Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Possibly engaging further stakeholders to present results at the end of activities, fairs, and events on the topic of new materials</u> - CTCON-UNIVPM [M31-M48]</i>		
	On-site concrete and pavement block will be developed - CTCON, UNIVPM, SOR [M14-M29]			
	Panel, reinforced with composite biobased rebars, will be developed as a facade solution - CTCON, SOR [M14-M29]			

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	Characterization tests of all products, including durability studies - CTCON, UNIVPM [M20-M30]		
Task 2.3	<i>Across project and Demo levels:</i> Numerical models for prototypes - VUB [M10-M19]		Scientific publications and conferences - VUB [M20-M43]
Leader: HOL	<i>Across Project and Demo levels:</i> Full-scale testing and manufacture development - HOL, VUB [M20-M29]		
	<i>Across Project and Demo levels:</i> Use alkali-activate cement for mortars - VUB, HOL [M31-M40]		
		<i>Across Demo and Cluster levels:</i> Characterisation of the central core in collaboration with materials suppliers – VUB, HOL, ARMACEL [M8-M10]	
Task 2.4	Production building elements for Demo - HOL [M13-M22]		
Leader: SOR	<i>Across Project and Demo levels:</i> Preparing building site - HOL, VUB [M20-M23]		
	<i>Across Project and Demo levels:</i> Assembling on-site demo - HOL, VUB [M23-M26]		
	<i>Across Project and Demo levels:</i> Developing of product considering manufacturing processes, prices, etc. - HOL, VUB [M26-M35]		
Task 2.5		Collect materials and components by CTCON, VUB HOL (TBC) - UNIVPM, CTCON, VUB HOL [M23-M35]	Scientific publications – UNIVPM [M37-M48]
		Design sustainable and circular materials – UNIVPM [M9]	
	<i>Across Demo, Cluster and Scientific engagement levels:</i> <u>Possibly engaging further stakeholders for collaboration with industrial partners</u> - UNIVPM [M37-M48]		

3.3.3 WP3 - Tracking, tracing and digital twinning of construction elements

The engagement activities within WP3 present the opportunity to utilize various approaches. A primary objective, applicable across all tasks, is to gather feedback from experts to validate the development process. These activities remain undefined, and the methodology for carrying them out may be introduced in upcoming deliverables. Another objective, specific to Task 3.2, focuses on collecting user requirements.

The road mapping exercise prompted WP3 partners to brainstorm on potential engagement activities that were previously overlooked. Table 3 below highlights seven engagement activities related to social innovation.

Task 3.1 - Development of a Digital Product Passport for construction

The task entails the collection of feedback from internal and external experts. The internal expert should be from Holland Composites on bio-based rebars, and from Sorigué on pavement. Instead, external stakeholders should be: UNE (Regulatory Board of Spain), Oficement (Cement Producers Association), Anehop, Andece, and IECA (Concrete Spanish Association). A questionnaire was mentioned by participants, which would be followed by further consultation with experts at M14 for the validation of the T3.1 solution. Furthermore, the activity at the demo level *Get missing information about demo products, agree with the producers on relevant scenarios to simulate*, at M16, may involve external stakeholders and it may be set up as collaborative workshops. The details must be discussed further with the task leader.

Task 3.2 - Development of a material traceability module for secure data sharing

The activity across Demo and Cluster levels *Organize data in a well-structured format for easy use by end-users*, from M28 to M33, will include engagement activities between M30 and M31 to define the needs and requirements of users. The method is still to be defined, but it should include standard user research. These activities should engage demo partners, but possibly also further stakeholders. Moreover, the two activities across Demo and Cluster levels *Implement Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) techniques* and *Develop a system to log user actions and event points*, in between M17-M22, are expected to include consultation of external experts at M19, to support decision-making. Such consultation may be organised in a collaborative form, enabling multiple iterations between partners and external experts on the solutions under development.

Task 3.3 - Definition of the Buildings' Material Passport

This task should include two consequential steps of engagement with external experts for collecting feedback on the development process, across the Demo and Cluster level. At first, a questionnaire will be possibly sent at M13, to experts both external and internal to RECONSTRUCT project. The internal expert should be BREEAM, while external ones should be part of CCRI or further consultancies such as Arup, Ellen MacArthur, and Ask

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Eva. The second step of expert consultation should happen at M28, engaging the latter for validation of the solution. The format of engagement is not defined, but it may entail collaborative activities.

Task 3.4 - Integration of modules into a dynamic 6D-BIM

In between M32 and M33, Task 3.4 should include the activity *External validation of the BIM with experts*: as mentioned above for Task 3.3, such validation may be facilitated through collaborative methods.

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Table 3: Outputs of the workshop (WP3)

	Project level	Demo level	Cluster level	Scientific engagement
Task 3.1 Leader: ITEC	Create the structure of the DPP - ITEC [M4-M7]	Put demo material and component data in ITEC database - ITEC, ICCS, TEE + WP5 [M10]	Validating that the DPP and BIM-model will have the same technical structure in both Brussels and Barcelona - ITEC [M7-M8]	Presentation of the project to CCRI and similar initiatives - ITEC [M15-48]
	Design of the structure of the DPP - ITEC, ICCS, TEE + WP5 [M8-M9]	Get missing information about demo products, agree with the producers on relevant scenarios to simulate – ITEC [M16]	<u>Possible first survey with external experts</u> - ITEC [M9]	Publish the DPP development, taking the NDAs into account, for disseminating beyond experts - ITEC [M20]
	Software structuring and programming of the DPP - ITEC, ICCS, TEE + WP5 [M10-M13]		<u>Possible involvement of external experts for validation</u> - ITEC [M14]	
	Design the connection with the BIM model to exchange data - ITEC [M10-M13]			
	Validation and testing of the data/structure - ITEC [M14]			
	Simulate actual demo products - ITEC + WP2 and WP4 partners [M16]			
Task 3.2 Leader: ICCS	Define the appropriate type of blockchain technology to host the data and contracting - ICCS, ITEC, TEE [M1-M16]		EU-wide Market research - ICCS [M7-M9]	
	Develop manual or automatic data registration - ICCS, ITEC, TEE [M10-M16]			
	Create interfaces and token management for tracing, tracking, and updating			

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	information dynamically – ICCS, ITEC, TEE [M10-M16]			
	<i>Across Project, Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Implement Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) techniques</u>- ICCS, ITEC, TEE [M17-M22]</i>			
	<i>Across Project, Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Develop a system to log user actions and event points for security maintenance, system monitoring, data recovery, and error correction.</u> - ICCS, ITEC, TEE [M17-M22]</i>			
	Include information on material type, quality, and quantities to fully characterize secondary materials for potential reuse in new buildings - ICCS [M24-M27]			
	<i>Across Project, Demo and Cluster levels: <u>Organize data in a well-structured format for easy use by end-users</u> – ITEC [M28-M33]</i>			
Task 3.3 Leader: ITEC	Investigate the structure of the MP - ITEC [M9-M12]	<u>Get missing information about demo products, agree with the producers on relevant scenarios to simulate</u> - ITEC [M28]	<u>Possible first survey with external experts</u> – ITEC [M13]	Presentation to CCRI and similar initiatives - ITEC [M28-48]
	Creation of the structure of the MP - ITEC, ICCS, TEE + WP3 partners M13]		<u>Possible involvement of external experts for validation</u> - ITEC [M28]	Publish the MP development, taking the NDAs into account, for disseminating beyond the circle of experts - ITEC [M37]
	Software structuring and programming of the MP – ITEC, ICCS, TEE [M14-M22]			
	Design the connection with the BIM model and the DPPs to exchange data, and define the MP - ITEC + BIM partners [M18-M24]			
	Design of reports on WP3 and WP5 - ITEC [M23-M24]			

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<p>Task 3.4</p> <p>Leader: TEE</p>	Validation and testing of the data/structure - ITEC [M25-M27]			
	Simulate actual demo building and baseline - ITEC + WP2, WP4, WP5 partners [M28-M31]			
	Collection of input from WP4 literature review – TEE [M13]	Get BIM from the demos - TEE [M13]	<u>External validation of the BIM with experts</u> - TEE [M32-M33]	Dissemination of data and/or results - TEE [M36]
	Rebuild the BIM from scratch – TEE [M15-M16]	Fine-tuning BIM to demos -TEE [M16-M17]		
	Develop the Dynamo scripts and Excel markups - TEE [M19-M22]	Coordination workshop with the WP2, WP4 and demos - [M18]		
	Integrate the scripts into Demo-BIM via Dynamo – TEE [M23-M24]	Coordination workshop with the WP4 and demo partners – TEE [M30]		
	Test with manual data, and compare performance against actual LCA data from the demo sites - TEE [M25]			
	Internal validation of the model, data cleaning – TEE [M26-M29]			
	Input from workshop with WP4 and demo partners, revision of model and data cleaning – TEE [M31]			
	Calculation of output for WP5 and WP7 on the global and LCA impact - TEE [M34]			

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3.3.4 WP5 - Monitoring and assessment of impacts

In WP5, engagement with external stakeholders revolves around three activities. Firstly, data should be collected from stakeholders for the monitoring and assessment calculation; this engagement does not qualify as a social innovation action, as it will consist of exchanges through emails or web calls. Secondly, stakeholders should provide feedback to validate the assessment achieved, entailing instead the possibility of setting up collaborative activities. Eventually, further stakeholders can be engaged with the aim of replicating the methodology developed by WP5.

The collaborative road mapping of WP5 activities allowed us to collect several already planned activities, and to identify potential avenues in which social innovation methods can be used in collaboration with WP5 partners.

Task 5.2 - Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing

The activity *Validation of LCA* at M42 should be engaging with both internal and external stakeholders, such as public administrations, designers, construction companies, and professional associations. For this reason, it was classified by participants as spanning across the Demo, the Cluster and the Scientific engagement levels. The engagement activities are still to be defined and should possibly include co-creation: T6.1 will support the task leader in the design of engagement activities.

Task 5.3 - Circularity Assessment & Symbiosis Potential

The activity *Calculation of symbiosis potential output*, to be carried out between M30 and M42, should engage with external industrial stakeholders. This holds true also for the activity *Validate input from external sources* from M41 to M42, and the category of external stakeholders is already identified in local waste management agencies, both from Barcelona and Brussels. Engagement with external stakeholders should be also carried out for the activity *Validate the assessment* (from M41 to M42) with research institutions and industrial stakeholders to check the usefulness of data. A further activity in Task 5.3 that may include collaborative engagement is *The possibility of including the new methodology in policy recommendations* from M43 to M46, which should involve stakeholders from the CCRI clusters. Such activity may draw on collaborative methods of policy design. Moreover, the activity *Possibilities for replication of SYM methodology*, set from M43 to M48 may be also developed further with the task leader. Even though the participants at first presented it as a “dissemination activity” among interested companies and research centres, training workshops on the methodology developed by the partner Simbiosy (SYM) may also be organised, during which new potential adopters are supported in collocating the new methodology in their existing workflows.

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Task 5.4 - *Social Impact Assessment*

This task entails the collection of data from external stakeholders and can also include some collaborative activities. The activities *Gathering input data from product manufacturing units*, from M33 to M34 and *Mapping BIM and material list*, from M34 to M35, should both collect data from external stakeholders, such as product manufacturers. The methods mentioned by partners are interviews and surveys: T6.1 can support partners in identifying further engagement methods concerning data collection. The activity *Validation of the S-LCA results with external stakeholders*, set at M41, is instead a potential participatory activity, which can be carried out with a workshop format.

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Table 4: Outputs of the workshop (WP5)

	Project level	Demo level	Cluster level	Scientific engagement
Task 5.1 Leader: ITEC	Monthly monitoring, to report work in other WPs, 2, 3, 4, 6 - ITEC [M10-M42]	Producing the plan for other assessments - ITEC, SYM, SOO, TEE [M1-M9]		
		Give a common structure to all assessments- ITEC [M1-M9]		
		Include work from other WPs into the assessment plan - ITEC [M25-M42]		
Task 5.2 Leader: ITEC		<u>Collecting data from materials and products suppliers</u> – ITEC [M30-M31]		
		BIM connection form for WP3 (T3.4) and WP4 (T4.2) - ITEC, TEE, VUB, SOO [M30-M37]		
		Matchmaking with existing databases - ITEC [M30-M31]		
		Double checking of matchmaking with materials and products suppliers - ITEC [M34-M35]		
		Update from WP3 - COMSA, TEE, VUB [M36]		

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		Run the LCA, asking for missing information from relevant stakeholders – ITEC [M38-M41]		
	<i>Across Demo, Cluster and Scientific Engagement levels: <u>validation of LCA</u> [M42]</i>			
Task 5.3 Leader: SOO	State of art of tools and methodologies for measuring circularity (with T6.5) - SOO, SYM, ITEC, VUB perhaps demo partners [M18]	Calculation of symbiosis potential inputs - ITEC, SOO, SYM, COMSA, SOR, HOL, VUB [M30-M40]	<u>Calculation of symbiosis potential outputs</u> - SOO [M30-M42]	<u>Possibilities for replication of Symbiosis (SYM) methodology</u> - SYM, SOO [M43-M48]
	Input from digital product passport - ICCS, ITEC [M30]		<u>Validate input from external sources</u> - SOO [M31-M32]	Communicate the results at regional and EU level - SOO [M43-M48]
	Input from external sources - Waste agencies in Catalonia, other externals in Brussels [M31-M32]		<u>Validate the assessment</u> - SOO [M41-M42]	
	Input from material passport - ITEC, TEE [M32-M36]		<u>Possibilities for include the new methodology in policy recommendation</u> - SOO, CCRI, cluster stakeholders [M43-M46]	
	Input for LCA calculation - ITEC, COMSA, HOL, TEE [M37-M40]			
	Circularity assessment - SYM, SOO, ITEC [M40]			
Task 5.4 Leader: TEE	Gathering input data from existing iTec's Database – TEE [M30-M31]	Gathering input data from demo sites, and material passport (WP3) [M30-M31]	<u>Gathering input data from product manufacturing units</u> - TEE [M32-M33]	Dissemination of results through conferences and publications [M42]
	Organising and processing the data to align with KPIs set in 5.1 – TEE [M32-M33]	<u>Mapping BIM and material list, with input from external stakeholders</u> – TEE [M34-M35]	<u>Validation of the S-LCA results</u> - TEE [M41]	

<p>Task 5.5</p> <p>Leader: TEE</p>	<p>Conduct the initial S-LCA – TEE [M35-M37]</p>	<p><u>Discuss the S-LCA results with internal stakeholders</u> [M38]</p>		
	<p>Conduct the assessment by incorporating the missing/updated information – TEE [M39-M40]</p>			
	<p>Methodology fine tune from T5.1 [M37-M38]</p>	<p><u>Workshop to assess clusters KPIs</u> [M38-M39]</p>		<p>Dissemination of results through conference proceedings to policy-informed external stakeholders [M46-M47]</p>
	<p>Initial assessment of clusters [M39-M40]</p>	<p><u>Workshop to assess methodology with Demo involved partners</u> [M44-M45]</p>		
	<p>Input data from T5.1, T5.2, T5.3, T5.4 [M41]</p>			
	<p>Simulations for MCDA [M42-M43]</p>			

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Considering the overall output of workshops, the collaborative road mapping led to the achievement of four main goals:

- i) Mapping of collaborations and engagements with stakeholders in the project;
- ii) Identification of activities related to social innovation;
- iii) Re-examination of expected engagements with external stakeholders;
- iv) Mutual understanding and coordination among partners, both within each WP and across different WPs.

The fulfilment of the goals of the road mapping is preliminarily confirmed by direct observations by workshop facilitators and on the feedback collected at the end of each workshop through the digital whiteboard. Participants were requested to express qualitative feedback on what they appreciated and what they did not appreciate about the road mapping workshop. Even though a more systematic assessment will be collected through the evaluation framework described in section 2.3, this preliminary feedback allowed us to confirm the strategy of collaborative roadmapping.

i) Mapping of collaborations and engagements with stakeholders in the project

It is worth considering that the technical development activities currently lack plans for integrating co-design activities with external stakeholders, with collaborative development primarily involving partners within the consortium, particularly in demo site activities.

Most likely, **engagements with external stakeholders will occur predominantly through local clusters**. Secondly, most interactions with externals not related to the clusters can be framed as “scientific engagement”. Since WP leaders are predominantly academic institutions responsible for specific tasks within the project, their main focus often lies in publishing results in scientific journals. Nevertheless, workshops have highlighted the potential for re-evaluating this approach to engagement, suggesting opportunities for more collaborative and co-design activities to be organized jointly with partners.

Besides providing an overview of the partners’ activities necessary for designing the social innovation strategy, the road mapping had a positive impact on the partners themselves. Participants in the workshops shared that they greatly appreciated the increased understanding of the whole project unfolding due to the road mapping:

“[a good thing about the workshop was] *Providing an overview of the activities of the whole WP. Not seen before. Very clarifying*” (from WP1 workshop).

“[a good thing about the workshop was] *Understanding activities' workflow in all the tasks*” (from the WP5 workshop)

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ii) Identification of activities related to social innovation

The mapping of activities allowed us to identify the most suitable avenues for introducing social innovation methodologies. For example, Task 1.5 in WP1 may adopt participatory methodologies to design the value chain of waste valorisation; Task 3.2 in WP3 may instead draw on further user research methods to collect requirements. These activities will be deepened by re-engaging WP partners, to implement best practices to facilitate the transition to circular construction. These interventions will allow us to integrate different kinds of expertise and extend collaboration across different stakeholders along the construction supply chain.

Partners participating in the workshops anticipated this possibility, and support by T6.1 was considered for the activities identified. A participant voiced the need to receive support in designing the stakeholder engagement activities:

“[the workshop could be better with] *study the [engagement and] dissemination possibilities and propose examples*” (from WP1 workshop)

Interestingly a participant explicitly suggested bringing further the use of the roadmap, anticipating the social innovation strategy adopted in Task 6.1:

“[the roadmap can be a] *Living document, useful for keeping track during the project*” (from WP2 workshop)

iii) Re-examination of expected engagements with external stakeholders

The road mapping exercise facilitated a critical reassessment of partners' assumptions regarding the involvement of external stakeholders. Probing partners about their objectives prompted reflection on the potential expansion of scope to incorporate bi-directional exchanges with external stakeholders.

For instance, as detailed in section 3.3, partners involved in Task 5.3 have started to consider the arrangement of training activities for external stakeholders during the collaborative road mapping workshop. These initial findings indicate that road mapping could serve as an effective strategy for catalysing a reconsideration and restructuring of engagements with external stakeholders within the project framework. This is also captured in the statements reported below:

“[a good thing about the workshop was to] *See collaborations between internal and external stakeholders*” (from WP5 workshop)

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“[a good thing about the workshop was to] *Start thinking about connection with demo/cluster partner and dissemination*” (from WP3 workshop).

iv) Mutual understanding and coordination among partners

Finally, the road mapping exercise allowed partners within each WP to understand the activities of other tasks: this will allow them to better synchronise their activities, and possibly increase collaboration across tasks:

“[a good thing about the workshop was being] *able to check the schedule of other tasks that impact my own ongoing and future tasks*’ (from the WP2 workshop)

“[a good thing about the workshop was] *Understanding the timeline of the Tasks from other partners, [it is] extremely important*” (from WP3 workshop)

“[a good thing about the workshop was to] *Validate with other partners the information of tasks*” (from WP5 workshop)

3.4 Monitoring Framework

The purpose of this section is to present a potential framework for evaluating the outcomes of the social innovation practices conducted in T6.1. Specifically, this framework aims to monitor both the objectives established for future engagement activities and the levels of social acceptance and satisfaction with the solutions and interventions developed throughout these activities.

The framework entails two main dimensions:

- **Monitoring of objectives:** The focus is on tracking the achievement of the objectives set for the engagement's activities. KPIs will be identified for each objective to facilitate quantitative and qualitative assessment. Regular monitoring and evaluation will allow for timely adjustments to engagement strategies, ensuring alignment with overarching project goals.
- **Social Acceptance and Satisfaction Assessment:** This dimension involves gathering feedback from both internal and external stakeholders regarding their perceptions, attitudes, and experiences with the solutions developed through social innovation practices. Surveys and interviews may be used to collect data on social acceptance and satisfaction. By systematically analysing this feedback, RECONSTRUCT partners can identify areas of strength and areas for improvement in the solutions developed and the engagement methodologies.

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Stakeholders' expectations, motivations, and acceptance are important aspects of RECONSTRUCT's success will be explored in T6.2.

Overall, the proposed framework provides a structured approach to evaluating the outcomes of the social innovation practices conducted within T6.1. Monitoring the achievement of objectives and assessing social acceptance and satisfaction enables RECONSTRUCT partners to make informed decisions, drive continuous improvement, and maximize the positive impact of their activities. Thus, the monitoring framework will be a key element of the dynamic learning agenda which will support reflexive learning among RECONSTRUCT partners.

The process for identifying the set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which is necessary to measure the two dimensions of the proposed framework (engagement objectives and social acceptance and satisfaction), will take advantage of the dynamic learning agenda set with the collaboration of project's partners and will follow the outlined iterative steps:

Figure 12: Iterative steps for collaborative definition of KPIs (CONS)

The collaborative identification of these pillars for each engagement activity will serve as a cornerstone for the development of robust KPIs aligned with common goals. This process will also contribute to cultivating a shared understanding of the objectives and outcomes sought through engagement efforts and will foster innovation within our project, by embracing diverse perspectives and harnessing the collective expertise of partners. This process will also contribute to identifying the KPIs for the social acceptance and satisfaction assessment of the solutions to be developed, whilst monitoring the potential involvement of external stakeholders, particularly those from the Circular Construction Clusters of Barcelona and Brussels. The pillars of the proposed monitoring framework will be discussed and agreed upon during a second round of collaborative roadmapping workshops. Once the pillars are defined and the KPIs are identified, a monitoring programme will be established.

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4 Conclusions and next steps

Figure 13: RECONSTRUCT approach to stakeholders' engagement (VUB, 2023)

D6.1 describes the RECONSTRUCT approach to social innovation by: a) framing key concepts, outlining the project's stakeholder engagement approach and the dynamic co-creation process that has been adopted and the rationale behind, b) describing the outputs of a series of collaborative road mapping workshops carried out with the project partners. Collaborative road mapping led to the achievement of four main goals:

1. Mapping of collaborations and engagements with stakeholders in the project;
2. Identification of activities related to social innovation;
3. Re-examination of expected engagements with external stakeholders;
4. Mutual understanding and coordination among partners, both within each WP and across different WPs.

Moving forward with the stakeholder engagement strategy, a key step is to cluster the various stakeholder activities identified within each work package (WP). The aim is to align these activities around the pivotal moments, or "**hotspots**," that are strategically programmed within our cluster and communication action plans (e.g. the open labs). These hotspots represent critical junctures where stakeholder involvement can significantly impact project outcomes. A second round of workshops for each WP may be needed to streamline the process.

As far as the **stakeholders' expectations** are concerned, complementing the research perspective with the "market" perspective is key to understanding how we can support stakeholders in overcoming challenges but also to gauge their interests and preferred levels of engagement. To initiate this process, as part of the stakeholder onboarding actions, a survey will be designed.

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T6.2 will first investigate key enablers and barriers to technology adopters' acceptance of CC through the literature review and workshops/interviews with the stakeholders at the demonstration sites. Interviews/focus groups with key stakeholders in the construction industry in two regions will then follow. It will then identify the gaps between CC technologies and their uptake by investigating the RECONSTRUCT technology providers' and adopters' perceptions via examining discrepancies between "user logic" and "design logic" derived through the workshops/interviews.

The stakeholder expectation survey will also play a crucial role in establishing an initial set of key performance indicators (**KPIs**) to follow up on. This baseline data will provide valuable insights into stakeholders' starting points and areas for improvement. As the project progresses, follow-ups with stakeholders will be implemented to monitor how their knowledge and perceptions evolve. The new data set will feed into D6.2 and D6.5.

A significant component of D6.2 is to follow up on the KPIs that will be established to evaluate the project's progress and effectiveness, specifically regarding the SI approach. This strategy enables this WP to assess the data collected from the KPIs to measure how well the project's SI strategies are performing against the set objectives. Ultimately, this helps to understand these strategies' impact and identify improvement areas.

An agenda, namely a list of priorities of **what we want to learn together**, will be co-created between consortium partners and external stakeholders during the **first stakeholder activities** to manage expectations from both sides as we develop knowledge together in the project. This dynamic learning agenda will be updated regularly through reflexive monitoring (a workshop to revisit the agenda that was created and adjust it where needed), as part of D6.2.

D6.5 is about packaging the project learnings in a replicable format for maximum transferability after the end of the project. This entails the evaluation of the monitoring KPIs.

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5 Annexes

Annexe1: Stakeholders prioritised for engagement during stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder	Segmentation (Helix)	Segmentation (Type)	Level of engagement	Objectives of engagement
BRUSSELS DEMO SITE				
Stad Gent	Government	Local	Inform	Policy recommendations
Stad Mechelen	Government	Local	Inform	Policy recommendations
De Vlaamse Waterweg	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Facilitair bedrijf	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Vlaamse overheid Beleidsdomein Mobiliteit en Openbare Werken	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Provincie Oost-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Provincie West-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Provinciale Ontwikkelingsmaatschappij West-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Lantis Beheersmaatschappij Antwerpen Mobiel	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
VLAIO Flanders innovation and entrepreneurship	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations
Municipality of Asse	Government	Local	Involve	Demo building permit
OVAM / Vlaanderen Circulair	Government	Regional	Inform	Policy recommendations

Ecocem (Netherlands)	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Demo, Business models
Silmaco (Belgium)	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Demo, Business models
Leviat (CRH group)	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
Masterbloc Gubbels	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
Sweco Belgium	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects
ResourceFull	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects
AB-Roads	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects
Living Lab Circulair Beton (VLAIO-project coordinated by Buildwise)	Industry	Clusters	Collaborate	The main channel to inform and consult stakeholders
Silma-Aldrich (Merck Group)	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Demo, Business models
Imerys (France)	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Demo, Business models
RECTICEL: provider of insulating solutions	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
3D weaving	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
DRIECON	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects
Betonadvies Gijko	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects
SBE	Industry	Engineering offices	Inform, maybe consult	Disseminate to as prescribers of concrete in projects

ETEX, looking for a prefab concrete element solution	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
Aurubis	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
Baumineral	Industry	Manufacturers	Involve	Business models
Buildwise	Academic	Research Centres	Consult	Leader of Living Lab Circular Concrete and gatekeeper to consult and disseminate to the sector
Stakeholder	Segmentation (Helix)	Segmentation (Type)	Level of engagement	Objectives of engagement
BARCELONA DEMO SITE				
GBCe (Green Building Council)	Government	National	Involve	Identify regulatory obstacles and how to overcome them
AVS (Spanish Association of Public Managers of Housing & Land)	Government	National	Inform	Development of a regulatory framework for public works
Ministerio (CTE + RC016)	Government	National	Inform	Development of a regulatory framework for public works
Catalan Housing Agency – Catalan agency for the management and renovation of social housing	Government	Regional	Collaborate	Spread information about the effectiveness of alternative material, increase acceptance
Generalitat (Ecoeficiencia)	Government	Regional	Consult	Spread information about the effectiveness of alternative material, increase acceptance
IBAVI	Government	Regional	Inform	Spread information about the effectiveness of

				alternative material, increase acceptance
ANDECE (precast concrete association)	Industry	Associations	Involve	Spread information about the effectiveness of alternative material, increase acceptance
GRCD.CAT (Chamber of Contractors)	Industry	Associations	Involve	Dissemination of precast products developed as an example of circular economy using concrete/cement
Oficemen (concrete & cement association)	Industry	Associations	Involve	Dissemination of precast products developed as an example of circular economy using concrete/cement
COMSA	Industry	Building companies	Collaborate	Spread information about the effectiveness of alternative material, increase acceptance; present application of new products in industry events
Sorigué	Industry	Manufacturers	Core	Spread information about the effectiveness of alternative material, increase acceptance; present application of new products in industry events

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Annexe 2: Collaborative road mapping template filled out with WP1 partners (ICONS, VUB, 2024)

[Link](#) to the digital whiteboard on miro.com

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Annexe 4: Collaborative road mapping template filled out with WP3 partners (ICONS, VUB, 2024)

[Link](#) to the digital whiteboard on miro.com

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Annexe 5: Collaborative road mapping template filled out with WP5 partners (ICONS, VUB, 2023)

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